

An Unlikely Ally: How the German Abwehr Aided the Success of Britain's Double Agents in WWII

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ABSTRACT

This article examines systemic faults in the German Abwehr during WWII, and how those faults were successfully exploited by British intelligence's Double Cross System. Britain's double agents were far from perfect and made many mistakes that should have indicated their duplicity to their Abwehr handlers. However, a culture of tolerating poor performance and internal resistance to the Nazi regime within the Abwehr allowed these agents to succeed. Their handlers neglected their duties due to perceived friendship and enjoyment of their post. The three Double Cross Agents examined in case studies are Dusko Popov, agent TRICYCLE, Lily Sergueiew, agent TREASURE, and Elvira de la Fuente Chaudoir, agent BRONX. Despite their tradecraft failures, they became some of the most successful and influential in deceiving the Nazis, especially for the Allied invasion on D-Day, due to Abwehr faults.

KEYWORDS: Abwehr, Admiral, Wilhelm Canaris, BRONX, Double Agent, Double Cross System, MI5, TREASURE, TRICYCLET, Twenty Committee

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History provides valuable lessons from which to learn. The study of past mistakes is important so that those same mistakes are not repeated. It is especially crucial in intelligence and counterintelligence when national security is at risk. The Double Cross System in World War II is regarded as one of the boldest and most

successful counterintelligence efforts ever made. It is important for case officers to understand the history of espionage tradecraft at the agent level and intelligence organization level. In most literature surrounding intelligence in WWII and the Double Cross system, the focus is on Allied intelligence, especially MI5. Studying

the case from a different perspective, in this case focusing on the Abwehr, allows a well-rounded understanding of intelligence organizations and tradecraft during one of the most influential periods for intelligence work. Current case officers can use this study to note what did and did not work in running a double agent and apply it to their own cases. Historical studies are a resource for learning and practical application, which is this paper's end goal.

This paper explores systemic problems in the German intelligence apparatus, specifically the Abwehr, to understand how British intelligence's double agents were able to succeed despite unknowingly indicating their duplicity to their German case officers. The three indicators of an agent's duplicity seen were poor tradecraft, a lavish lifestyle in which the agent lived beyond the means of their German salary, and the failure to produce quality information, or intelligence, for their German handlers. All indicators were consistently overlooked by Abwehr case officers who either thought nothing of them or did not care enough to investigate. Internal resistance to the Nazi regime and a culture of tolerating poor performance in the Abwehr was exploited by British Intelligence's Double Cross system which succeeded despite the agents' indiscretion, living beyond their means, and failure to provide intelligence, indicating duplicity to their Abwehr handlers.

Methodology

This study will employ a variety of primary and secondary sources. To analyze the Abwehr, Luran Paine's *German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr*, Macquarie University student Maria Atkins' honors thesis, *Why Is the Abwehr Misunderstood? Explaining the Historical Controversy over German Military Intelligence, 1935-1945*, and Harry Carl Schaub's *General Labousen and the Abwehr* were most useful. These secondary sources describe and analyze Abwehr organization, tradecraft, and leadership. To bring in a different perspective, a declassified Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) report titled *The German Intelligence Service and the*

War examined the Abwehr's capabilities and failures noticed by United States intelligence. These sources will be used to provide a history and description of the Abwehr to better understand the sprawling, confusing component of the German intelligence apparatus in WWII. A brief history and explanation of the Double Cross system will also be provided, largely coming from a report by the head of the Twenty Committee which ran the system, J.C. Masterman.

The case studies of the Double Cross agents TREASURE, BRONX, and TRICYCLE will show Abwehr faults as seen through their German case officers, as well as common indicators that an agent had been flipped, which their case officers missed or ignored. Analysis in this section was derived from declassified MI5 files for the three Double Cross agents mentioned above. Information in the files was cross-referenced with the agents' autobiographies and diaries, and biographies.

These two sections combined create a comprehensive study of how the systemic faults and vulnerabilities of the Abwehr were exploited by MI5 and their double agents, despite the double agents' indications of their duplicity to their Abwehr handlers. The paper will conclude with a section regarding the study's usefulness for current case officers and recommendations for further research.

Ambiguous Files, Bias, and Vast Literature

The first limitation to this research is that the declassified MI5 files were difficult to understand and generally lacked greater context. For example, the file on Elvira de la Fuente Chaudoir, agent BRONX, is a simple summary of her communications to MI5. There were no details to analyze indicators of duplicity to the Abwehr. Some files are handwritten notes, and the writing was often too messy to decipher. Many of the communication transcripts included coded references that cannot be understood without greater context. Therefore, the files have acted as a fact check for information found in other sources when they could

not be understood on their own. The most useful source to combat this limitation was J.C. Masterman's report, *The Double Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*, and Ben Macintyre's *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. Information from the agents' autobiographies and diaries was also useful but had to be used carefully due to the potential for bias exaggerating each one's personal success.

A second limitation to this research is that the literature on intelligence in WWII, the Double Cross system, the double agents individually, and MI5 is so vast that time did not allow for all of it to be read for this paper. The Abwehr and Double Cross system both have a complicated history and story, which is told slightly differently in each source. This paper emphasizes common points found in all sources and more niche information is cross-referenced with the primary sources to check for and note discrepancies between versions of the story. The three agents to be studied were chosen because they appear in most sources and played a great role in the Twenty Committee's ultimate goal, deception covering the Allied landings on D-Day.

The Double Cross System: The Basics

The British Intelligence Services, MI5 (the Secret Service) and MI6 (the Secret Intelligence Service), recognized the value of double agents prior to the beginning of WWII.¹ Before war broke out in 1940, there was public fear of a massive German spy ring in Britain.² The British intelligence services began hunting the spies but found the ring to be much smaller than rumors claimed.³ Realizing they could turn these agents and use them to their advantage; they began doing so

and the system grew.⁴ Guy Liddell, director of MI5 during WWII, divided MI5 into sections. Section B was counterespionage, subsequently subsection B1A became the "Double Cross" Section with Thomas Argyll, "Tar," Robinson in the lead.⁵ Within B1A a smaller committee was established to run the Double Cross agents. In a comical play on words, the name "Twenty Committee" was chosen because the roman numerals for twenty, XX, are a double cross, just like their agents.⁶ The Twenty Committee was comprised of intelligence directors from the military branches, MI5, MI6, Home Forces, and Home Defense, headed by Chairman John (J.C.) Masterman.⁷ Their first official meeting was on 2 January 1941, after the double agents had been "haphazardly" ran by MI5 and MI6 since 1939.⁸ In 1941 the XX Committee hesitantly began to guess that they controlled the enemy system; but by 1943 Tar Robertson realized that every single German agent in Britain was indeed controlled by MI5.⁹ The committee continued to meet every week until the war ended in 1945.¹⁰ The entire system included thirty-nine double agents, but the three in this study are Dusko Popov, agent TRICYCLE; Elvira de la Fuente Chadoir, agent BRONX; and Lily Sergueiew, agent TREASURE.

The Abwehr: Basics, Structure, and Early (Non)Success

The Abwehr was the perfect loophole to start rebuilding the intelligence apparatus in post-World War I Germany. Under restrictions imposed by the Treaty of Versailles, Germany was not allowed to have any offensive intelligence organizations.¹¹ This meant

¹ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. London: Yale University Press, 1972. 36.

² Caddell, Joe. "The Long Armistice." Lecture, April 4, 2024.

³ Caddell, Joe. "The Long Armistice."

⁴ Caddell, Joe. "The Long Armistice."

⁵ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 36, 38.

⁶ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 4.

⁷ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 43.

⁸ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. 61-63.

⁹ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 4-5.

¹⁰ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. 63.

¹¹ Paine, "German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr" 6.

their intelligence services were not to engage in information collection efforts meant to harm an adversary. They could only collect information to protect their nation. The Abwehr was perfect because it was officially classified as a defensive intelligence agency¹² The word *Abwehr* translates to “defense” in English.¹³ As WWII progressed, the Abwehr became engaged in more offensive intelligence work. From 1935 to 1944 it operated as a secret department under the Oberkommando der Wehrmacht (OKW).¹⁴ It had headquarters in Berlin and many out-stations in other parts of Germany and several foreign countries.¹⁵ The Abwehr followed the pattern of military organization; it was static when the armies were occupational and mobile when they were operational.¹⁶ It had three primary sections. Section I controlled branch offices, created espionage networks, and included a counter-espionage department.¹⁷ Section II focused on sabotage and “special duties,” which had different meanings at different points in the war; and Section III oversaw counter-sabotage, counterespionage, and security.¹⁸ In short, they respectively were operational espionage, sabotage and subversion, and counterespionage.¹⁹

The Abwehr’s success fluctuated. According to the U.S.’s CIA, Section I was consistently unsuccessful.²⁰ The German intelligence services were never able to develop an adequate training program for their spies.²¹ Being sent into a hostile country with no proper training lowered the spy’s chance of survival and led to easier capture and turning by the adversary. The fact that all of Germany’s agents in Britain had been turned

and were controlled by British intelligence demonstrates that Abwehr offensive espionage was largely a failure. Sections II and III had better success but still lacked the ability to gain a clear intelligence advantage. Section II, sabotage and subversion, was successful in areas the Germans had diplomatic advantages and/or some control, but not in places where these advantages laid with the Allies.²² If they were unsuccessful in the arena where it mattered most, where Germany had little to no advantage, was the section truly successful at all? The low success rate of section II may also be due to its leader’s resistance to the Nazi regime, which will be examined in the next section. Finally, the CIA report stated that section III was “generally successful” because it was able to penetrate Allied intelligence services in the Low Countries in the beginning of the war, and consistently penetrated resistance movements in that area.²³

The Abwehr Norm: Internal Resistance in Leadership and Poor Performance

Admiral Wilhelm Canaris, head of the Abwehr, saw his appointment, and the organization itself, as a way to preserve Germany and undermine Hitler. In post-war interrogations, former Abwehr officer and close confidant of Canaris, Captain Franz Maria Leidig said “Canaris began conspiring against the Nazis as soon as he assumed Abwehr control.”²⁴ Canaris was a German patriot with the goal of preserving Germany, not the Nazis in charge.²⁵ Canaris disagreed with Nazi ideals but had originally agreed with Hitler’s rearmament and

¹² Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 6.

¹³ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 6.

¹⁴ Central Intelligence Agency. CIA-RDP78-03362A002500070002-3 “The German Intelligence Service and the War.” December 1, 1945. Released February 3, 2014.

¹⁵ CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 1.

¹⁶ CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 1.

¹⁷ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 10-11.

¹⁸ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 11.

¹⁹ CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 1.

²⁰ CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 2.

²¹ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 14.

²² CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 2.

²³ CIA, “The German Intelligence Service and the War” 2.

²⁴ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 29.

²⁵ Paine, “German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr” 28.

reorganization plans to restore Germany.²⁶ He supported the buildup of the German fleet and a strong economy, and he believed the Generals on Hitler's staff could control him and oust him if needed.²⁷ When he learned the extent of Hitler's true plan, he considered it "suicidal" for Germany.²⁸ Since before the war started, the Abwehr's goal was to remove the Nazi regime; its biggest enemy was the government it served.²⁹ Amid tensions and turf wars between the different agencies of the German intelligence apparatus, Canaris fought to preserve the Abwehr so that he had a position powerful enough to make an impact in destroying Hitler's regime.³⁰ Examples of his efforts were his overestimation of British troops to dissuade Hitler from invading Britain, leaving out information in reports regarding Operation TORCH (the successful Allied invasion of North Africa), and directly aiding the Allies by providing secret communications, codes, etc.³¹

To accomplish his goal, Canaris recruited Abwehr leaders that shared his morals. He recruited General Erwin von Lahousen who eventually headed Section II and was a great aid to the internal resistance. Lahousen was the first Austrian to be selected by Canaris to join the Abwehr leadership.³² When he first joined, unsure how to properly address his new bosses, Lahousen rendered the Hitler salute. Canaris' response was a slow lowering of Lahousen's arm while talking and Canaris'

deputy Hans Oster responded with "is it, then, your intention to serve willingly the greatest criminal of all times?"³³ Lahousen's brother had a record of anti-Nazi views, so Heinrich Himmler, the third most powerful man in the Third Reich, was against Lahousen's Abwehr appointment.³⁴ Canaris was able to successfully defend the appointment and instructed Lahousen not to bring any National Socialists to Berlin.³⁵ The special instruction to not bring any National Socialists to Abwehr headquarters, the lowering of Lahousen's salute, and recruitment of fellow anti-Nazis paint Canaris as an unlikely ally to the Allied cause. His provision of misinformation to Hitler directly aided the Double Cross system, who's agents carried out deception operations to cover it.

Many Abwehr case officers were lazy, entitled, or simply did not care about their job. This was beneficial for the double agents because it made deceiving their German handlers that much easier. One such example was Major Emile Kliemann, Lily Sergueiew's German case officer. Kliemann was stationed in Paris when it was under German occupation, giving him a pleasant life there.³⁶ Living in a luxurious apartment, he was enjoying the benefits of being an Abwehr spymaster but not taking his role seriously.³⁷ Macintyre and Sergueiew note in their works that Kliemann was hours late for their very first meeting, when he was to recruit her.³⁸ Kliemann was notorious for taking overly

²⁶ Paine, "German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr" 31.

²⁷ Paine, "German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr" 28.

²⁸ Paine, "German Military Intelligence in WWII: The Abwehr" 31.

²⁹ Atkins, Renate Katharina Maria. "Why Is the Abwehr Misunderstood? Explaining the Historical Controversy over German Military Intelligence, 1935-1945". Macquarie University, May 3, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.25949/21424656.v1.2>.

³⁰ Atkins, Renate Katharina Maria. "Why Is the Abwehr Misunderstood? Explaining the Historical Controversy over German Military Intelligence, 1935-1945". 3.

³¹ Atkins, Renate Katharina Maria. "Why Is the Abwehr Misunderstood? Explaining the Historical Controversy over German Military Intelligence, 1935-1945". 3.

³² Schaub, Harry Carl. "General Lahousen and the Abwehr Resistance." *International Journal of Intelligence and CounterIntelligence* 19, no. 3 (June 2006): 538–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08850600500483855>.

³³ Schaub, Harry Carl. "General Lahousen and the Abwehr Resistance."

³⁴ Schaub, Harry Carl. "General Lahousen and the Abwehr Resistance."

³⁵ Schaub, Harry Carl. "General Lahousen and the Abwehr Resistance."

³⁶ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 24.

³⁷ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 24.

³⁸ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 25, and Sergueiew, Lily. *I Worked Alone: Diary of a Double Agent in World War II Europe*. Edited by Mary

extended periods of time to contact his agents, putting his new life in France ahead of his Abwehr duties. He will be further discussed in Lily Sergueiew's case study.

The Double Cross Agents' Indicators

Great Intentions, Poor Tradecraft: Lily Sergueiew, Agent TREASURE

Agent TREASURE had the best intentions but rather poor tradecraft. Sergueiew's indiscreet behavior and consistent lack of quality intelligence should have indicated her duplicity to Major Kliemann. After seeing her home country, France, fall to the Nazis she developed the idea to become a German spy, but betray them as a double agent.³⁹ She had a friend that worked for the German intelligence services who had previously offered her a job, so to put her plan into action she wrote him a letter expressing interest in the position.⁴⁰ Sergueiew was not discreet about her intentions. Before she left for her recruitment meeting, she told her sister about her plans.⁴¹ To see if a lover trusted her, she told United States Army Air Force Lieutenant Kenneth Larson of her role as a British double agent.⁴² Telling other people of her double life was an immense security risk and a tradecraft failure. It could have led to German discovery of her duplicity which would have had the potential to disrupt the entire Double Cross system. In addition to indiscretion, Sergueiew did not handle routine interviews well and went "off script" on her cover stories.⁴³ In customs interviews Sergueiew was flustered and could not answer simple questions such as her name, date and place of birth, and reasons for travelling.⁴⁴

Barbier. Jefferson, NC: McFarland & Company, Inc., Publishers, 2014. 25.

³⁹ Sergueiew, Lily. *I Worked Alone: Diary of a Double Agent in World War II Europe*. 13.

⁴⁰ Sergueiew, Lily. *I Worked Alone: Diary of a Double Agent in World War II Europe*. 13.

⁴¹ Sergueiew, Lily. *I Worked Alone: Diary of a Double Agent in World War II Europe*. 15.

⁴² The National Archives of the UK (TNA): KV 2/465. Document 1, page 7.

Sergueiew's handler, Kliemann, should have picked up on these indicators but either did not notice or simply ignored them so that he could continue his lavish Parisian lifestyle. Another indication he missed was Sergueiew's lack of quality reporting. She would show up to meetings with Kliemann empty handed.⁴⁵ The repeated failure to produce intelligence alone should have raised Kliemann's suspicions. There is no evidence Kliemann took note of Sergueiew's indiscretion or interview failures. He either did not notice due to negligence of duty or desire to keep his station, not reporting it so that he stayed in good graces with the Abwehr leadership. Thus, Lily Sergueiew was able to successfully continue spying as a double agent.

Living Lavish: Elvira de la Fuente Chaudoir, Agent BRONX

Agent BRONX was very intelligent and had wonderful potential, but her gambling habit and luxurious lifestyle went beyond the means of her German salary. Chaudoir was recruited by British intelligence because they knew she needed money, and she had a Peruvian passport that would allow easy travelling during the war; they then dangled her in front of the Germans as a potential spy.⁴⁶ Agent BRONX was motivated by greed and boredom. Her gambling habit and desire for expensive goods forced MI5 to pay her increasing sums of money, which went unnoticed by her German handlers.⁴⁷

The Germans wholeheartedly believed in BRONX, demonstrating the negligence of her Abwehr case officers. If they had been doing their job correctly, they would have noticed the indication of duplicity via her

⁴³ TNA: KV 2/465. Document 1, page 13.

⁴⁴ TNA: KV 2/465. Document 1, page 13.

⁴⁵ Sergueiew, Lily. *I Worked Alone: Diary of a Double Agent in World War II Europe*. 65-67

⁴⁶ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 19.

⁴⁷ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 133.

finances. BRONX, however, was a successful agent. In 1944, BRONX was given a code to tell the Germans where to expect the anticipated Allied invasion.⁴⁸ She messaged that an invasion would take place at the Bay of Biscay around 15 June 1944, part of a British deception plan to keep a German panzer division in the Bordeaux area and away from the invasion site at Cherbourg.⁴⁹ The deception worked, and the Germans continued to believe in BRONX. They continued asking her for invasion locations and awaited news from her until the end of the war and in post-war rebuilding.⁵⁰ Chaudoir's financial habits should have raised suspicion in the Abwehr. Based on her continued success, however, it can be concluded that her case officers either did not notice or did not care enough to pass it on. BRONX's case exemplifies why all details of an agent must be examined, because an investigation into her finances would have shown her duplicity to the Abwehr.

A Lack of Intelligence: Dusko Popov, agent TRICYCLE

Dusko Popov, agent TRICYCLE, was under brief suspicion by the Germans due to lack of quality intelligence. Due to bias from perceived friendship, however, his handlers defended him, allowing his double agent career to flourish. Popov was recruited into German intelligence by an old friend named Johnny Jebsen, but Popov already had an idea to become a double upon recruitment.⁵¹ Just after being recruited as a German agent in 1940, Popov approached First Secretary of the British Embassy John Dew to tell him the Germans had recruited him; Dew promptly put Popov in contact with British intelligence.⁵²

Popov's personal relationship with his Abwehr handlers allowed him to succeed as a double agent after being suspected of betrayal. In March 1942 the Germans became suspicious of TRICYCLE due to a consistent lack of quality intelligence.⁵³ An MI5 memorandum dated 3 April 1943 reported that TRICYCLE had visited his handlers in Lisbon and re-established their confidence in him through the personal friendship he formed with them.⁵⁴ The same memo stated that TRICYCLE had finally heard from his German handlers after a period of silence and was scolded for the lack of reporting but reassured of payment.⁵⁵ After being placed under suspicion by another Abwehr officer who believed he became a double when he went to the United States, TRICYCLE's direct contacts, his Lisbon handlers, strongly advocated for him. The suspicion was dropped, and TRICYCLE went on to be one of the most successful Double Cross Agents.⁵⁶ TRICYCLE was able to deceive his handlers who ensured his success, by charming them into friendship. Had the case officers not crossed the line between professional and personal relationships, TRICYCLE may have been caught, bringing the whole system down with him.

Conclusions and Suggestions for Future Research

MI5's Double Cross system is regarded as one of the boldest and most successful counterintelligence operations ever attempted, but that success can be linked to systemic faults in the Abwehr. The Double Cross agents were not perfect. Some common indicators of their duplicity were poor tradecraft, living a lavish lifestyle beyond the means of their German salary, and lack of intelligence reporting. They

⁴⁸ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. 161.

⁴⁹ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. 161-162.

⁵⁰ Macintyre, Ben. *Double Cross: The True Story of the D-Day Spies*. 345.

⁵¹ Popov, Dusko. *Spy/Counterspy: The Autobiography of Dusko Popov*. New York: Grosset & Dunlap, 1974. 1.

⁵² Popov, Dusko. *Spy/Counterspy: The Autobiography of Dusko Popov*. 26.

⁵³ The National Archives of the UK (TNA): KV 2/852. Document 2, page 21.

⁵⁴ TNA: KV 2/852. Document 2, pages 19-21.

⁵⁵ TNA: KV 2/852. Document 1, page 71.

⁵⁶ TNA: KV 2/852. Document 2, pages 19-21.

succeeded by exploiting two systemic issues in the Abwehr, internal resistance and toleration of poor performance. Abwehr leadership was plagued by internal resistance to the Nazi regime. Abwehr chief, Admiral Wilhelm Canaris, was opposed to Hitler and led movements to oust him. He recruited fellow anti-Nazis into Abwehr leadership to further his efforts. Thus, the Abwehr was never loyal to Nazi Germany, and faults could be easily exploited by the Allies without the Abwehr caring very much.

J.C. Masterman, head of the Twenty Committee that ran the Double Cross system, concluded his report of the system with “almost always when a real blunder was made by the Germans it was traceable to the fact that the Abwehr official implicated was governed by personal considerations; he was making money out of the agent or gaining prestige from him or even only making his post in some comfortable neutral haven secure, and in consequence he could not and would not judge the agent and the agent’s work, dispassionately or even honestly.”⁵⁷ This was seen by examining three agents, TREASURE, BRONX, and TRICYCLE. In each case their Abwehr handler dismissed or never noticed the agent’s indication of duplicity due to laziness, enjoyment of their post, or a sense of comfort due to friendship. The case officers themselves tolerated poor performance, and resistance in Abwehr leadership allowed them to get away with it, as the leaders were focused on defeating Hitler, not the Allies. Current case officers can learn many lessons from the Abwehr’s history and the Double Cross system. At the organizational level, they can learn what signs to look for in a leader whose ideas go against the organization’s mission. If any Abwehr case officers were hardline Nazis, they could have taken time to analyze their leaders and report back to Nazi leadership. It is never a good idea to blindly follow someone but in this historical case it is good the Abwehr leaders were anti-Nazi and wanted to defeat a great evil. At the individual level, case officers can study the indicators of each

agent and look for similar indicators in their own. The case studies teach them to pay close attention to all details, especially who their agents are closely speaking with and their finances. The case of TRICYCLE emphasizes the importance of a professional relationship boundary. Case officers should never let their agent get so close that they believe everything they say since they’re a “friend.” Negligence of duty has dire consequences. The Abwehr case officers of TREASURE, BRONX, and TRICYCLE exemplify that because their agents went on to be some of the most successful for the Allies. Case officers, take note of these mistakes, and do not repeat them.

This paper examined just three of the thirty-nine Double Cross agents and their Abwehr handlers. Further research should expand to every agent and their handlers. More research into the personal lives of the Abwehr case officers would be beneficial to the existing literature. Their finances could show why they neglected their duties; perhaps they were solely in it for the money. Psychological evaluations would give insight to the agents’ and handlers’ minds, but that is limited to ones that have surviving diaries and autobiographies. The literature of the Double Cross system is vast, but there is always more to learn. Instead of being content with everything that is known, future researchers should consider exploring the above pathways.

⁵⁷ Masterman, J.C. *The Double-Cross System in the War of 1939 to 1945*. 187.

Author Biography

Emily Lewis is a 2025 graduate of the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill with a Bachelor of Arts degree in Peace, War, and Defense concentrating in International Security and Intelligence, with a Political Science second major and History minor. She recently completed the National Security and International Affairs Research Internship at the Institute of World Politics in Washington, D.C., where she is now a candidate for a Master of Arts degree in Strategic Intelligence Studies. Originally from the small town of Stanley, North Carolina, Emily now resides in Arlington, Virginia with her husband.

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